

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AHMAD RUFAl****FIRST NAME: SHAMSUDDEEN****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 12%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2007 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary purpose of an abstract in a research paper?
 - To provide a concise summary description of the study, including a statement of the problem, purpose, scope, research tradition, data sources, methodology, key findings, and implications.¹**
 - To provide a detailed explanation of the methodology used.
 - To list all the references used in the research.
 - To discuss the background literature in depth.

2. What is the primary purpose of a literature review in a research paper?
 - To provide a clear and balanced picture of current leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the topic or subject of study.²**

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 68.

² Ibid., 352.

- To summarize the entire research study.
 - To discuss the research methodology in detail.
 - To present the research findings and conclusions.
3. What is meant by identifying gaps in the literature?
- A Notes gaps, debates, or shortcomings in the literature and provides a rationale for the study.³**
 - Ignoring existing research that does not align with your views.
 - Listing all the sources without any particular order.
 - Finding sources that are difficult to understand.
4. Which of the following is a characteristic of qualitative research?
- Research takes place within natural contexts.⁴**
 - Is always objective and replicable.
 - Focuses on numerical data and statistical analysis.
 - Is Used when a research study needs to confirm or test a theory or a hypothesis.
5. What is a mixed research method?
- It is a distinct and complex research approach that intentionally and systematically uses both qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods concurrently in one study.⁵**
 - It is a research approach that relies solely on numerical data.
 - A method that involves random sampling.
 - An approach that uses historical data only.

³ Ibid., 77.

⁴ Ibid., 139.

⁵ Ibid., 136.

6. Researchers can commit plagiarism when writing academic papers.
- Quote, paraphrase, or summarize a source but fail to cite it.**⁶
 - Ensure citation when ideas, data, or methods from other sources are used.
 - Paraphrasing information and citing all sources correctly.
 - Copy and paste from sources with proper citations.
7. Why is citation essential in academic writing?
- To give credit to the original authors.**⁷
 - To make the paper longer.
 - To confuse the readers.
 - To fill space in the document.
8. What additional information is typically required when citing an online source?
- The URL or DOI.**⁸
 - The publisher's location.
 - The number of pages.
 - The author's email address.
9. How should sources be integrated into a literature review?
- By synthesizing and connecting different sources to build a coherent narrative.**⁹
 - By discussing each source separately without any connections.
 - By focusing only on the sources that are easiest to understand.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 80.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 139.

⁸ Ibid., 144.

⁹ Ibid., 383.

- By listing sources without any critical analysis.

10. In Chicago style, where are footnotes typically placed in the text?

- At the bottom of the page where the reference occurs.¹⁰**
- At the end of the document.
- In the bibliography.
- At the beginning of each chapter.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 56.